

OPTIMIZATION OF COWL AND RAMP ANGLES OF SUPERSONIC INTAKE OF RAMJET ENGINE

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Abstract:

Supersonic inlet diffusers plays an important role in the performance of air-breathing engines, particularly in the context of ramjet engines. Ramjet engines are known for their simplicity and high speed capabilities, making them valuable in aircraft and missile propulsions. The efficiency of a ramjet engine was highly dependent on the performance of supersonic inlet diffuser. The diffuser was responsible for slowing down and compressing the the incoming supersonic air(mach number 3 to 5) into subsonic air(mach number 0.3 to 0.4) for combustion in the engine. So, the performance of the ramjet engine was affected by supersonic inlet diffuser. Supersonic inlet diffuser performance improved by suitable cowl and ramp geometry design. Present study focuses on finding optimal cowl and ramp angles of supersonic inlet diffuser. Pressure recovery and outlet mach number were numerically obtained at cowl angle(11° , 12° , 13° , and 14°), first ramp angles(3° , 4° , and 5°) and second ramp angles(21° , 22° , and 23°).

Keywords: Ramjet engine, cowl angle, ramp angles, mach number, pressure recovery.

1. Introduction:

CFD models predicted both on and off design performance of subsonic diffusers, bleeding systems, viscous effects, and variable -geometry intakes[3]. The supersonic inlet geometry stabilised the inlet operation for diverse speeds [1]. Larger cowl deflection angle improved performance of supersonic intake in the absence of back pressure, but smaller angles (around 2°) will results in increased performance in the presence of back pressure in a 2D numerical study(RANS solver with a k-w turbulence model)[2]. SUPIN was a computational tool designed for crafting and evaluating external-compression supersonic inlets for aircraft cruising at speeds ranging from Mach 1.6 to 2.0. The tool assessed aerodynamic performance by examining flow rates, total pressure recovery, and drag, leveraging a combination of analytic, empirical, and numerical methods for rapid analysis. SUPIN divided the inlet flowfield into manageable segments, facilitating geometry and aerodynamic modeling[4].

The ideal supersonic intakes were designed using Theta-Beta - Mach relations and modelled in CAD software. The ideal supersonic intakes were optimised by varying cowl deflection angles and for maximising pressure recovery with intake bleed[5]. Sharp cowl

leading edge improved the combustion stability and reduced shock wave boundary layer interaction which was seen through numerical simulations[6].

The two key designs, i) a small cowl offset violating the shock on lip condition and ii) an internal wedge angle forcing a strong oblique shock optimised total pressure recovery and minimised intake pressure drag of an external compression supersonic intake[7]. Ramjet engine was more suitable for supersonic and hypersonic flows due to its simple construction, free of rotating parts, but flow is more complex in subsonic and supersonic regimes[8]. CFD tools applied to design intakes of high speed air breathing engines by solving 3D Navier-stokes equation with SST k- ω turbulence model, which matched with the experimental data[9]. Supersonic inlets facilitated high angle manoeuvres and high speed slides without disrupting flow. Disruptive flow was quantified using numerical indices such as density, velocity and viscous force[10]. Implementing ramjet engines could reduce missile weight by nearly 90%, but posed challenges such as mismatched air supply and demand. Unlike aircraft, adjustable intake and nozzle geometries were generally avoided in missile design for cost-efficiency. Intake design factors and proposed a design tested through computational fluid dynamics simulations in ANSYS Fluent, focusing on total pressure recovery and mass flow rate characteristics across Mach numbers, angles of attack, and sideslips[11]. A prototype inlet was designed in SolidWorks and analysed using ANSYS Fluent 15.0 to assess static pressure rise, total pressure recovery, and flow distortion. It resulted that with increasing cowl angle led to higher flow distortion and reduced total pressure recovery, while decreasing, it reduced separation region size[12]. Advanced inlet design methods leveraged high-fidelity computational fluid dynamics and machine learning technologies, such as deep learning, to automate feature extraction and establish fast prediction models. By combining performance intelligent prediction models with multi-objective intelligent evolution algorithms, optimal inlet designs were achieved[13]. A computational study investigated flow physics within a mixed compression air intake at a design Mach number of 2.2, using RANS equations and k- ω turbulence model in ANSYS. Arrays of air jets with varying hole counts and equal spacing were tested, by maintaining constant injection pressure. Results showed improved performance with proper air jets spacing, facilitating vortex mixing with freestream flow and controlling shock-induced separation. An array of four Air jets holes on the ramp surface results in optimal performance through flow control and intake efficiency improved[14]. A Mach 4 axisymmetric supersonic intake SR-71 scaled model assessed for static and total pressure measurements within the duct and employed the colour schlieren technique to observe shock effects on external flow. Surface correction of the cone was attempted to enhance pressure recovery, while varying blockage areas at the exit aided in locating the normal shock for minimum pressure loss[15]. Two and three ramp 2D supersonic intake configurations were analysed using MATLAB for theoretical calculations and CATIA for geometry creation. Simulated through ANSYS Fluent at Mach 2.8, resulted in overall performance in terms of Mach number and pressure recovery post-normal shock[16]. CFD simulations were conducted on 2D supersonic mixed compression intake with two external

ramps in rhoCentralFoam of OpenFOAM, under steady compressible flow across Mach numbers ranging from 5 to 6.5, at varying angles of attack and a flight altitude of 26 km. Results indicated a 20% improvement in compression ratio (static pressure and temperature) and a 16.7% increase in captured mass flow[17]. A supersonic intake of four intake symmetric cross or X configuration missile analysed at mach number range of 1.8 to 2.5, an angle-of-attack(AoA) range of $0^\circ \leq \text{AoA} \leq 10^\circ$, and a low altitude condition of 5-10 km. By Passive bleed systems and integration with an ogive nosed forebody resulted in improved total pressure recovery (TPR) and mass flow ratio (MFR)[18]. The isolator design featured cowl convergence angles ranging from 0° to 16° and included a blockage adjustor at the exit. Nano-tracer Planar Laser Scattering (NPLS) technique and pressure measurement were used for flow visualisation and characterization. Results revealed distinct flow structures such as supersonic boundary layer, separation flow, shock waves, Mach disk, and slip lines. Favourable contraction ratios provided moderate starting performance, while excessive or deficient contraction angles resulted in harder starting due to pressure rise and severe separation. Pressure profiles indicated optimal pressure endurance with an 8° cowl convergence angle, and flow deceleration to sonic occurred as blockage ratio approached choking the isolator[19]. Sensitivity analyses determined a minimum mesh size of 300 and k- ω SST turbulence model settings for optimal accuracy and computation time. New inlet shapes were designed to minimise drag coefficient and maximise static and total compression ratios. The designs prioritised minimising interference and replacing normal shock with gradual compression from oblique shocks[20].

1.1 Supersonic Intakes:

Supersonic intake reduces the supersonic flow ($M > 1$) into subsonic flow by generating oblique shock waves at the tip of cowl and ramp corners and followed by normal shock waves at the throat of the intake due to ramming effect as shown in the fig.1. Here compression is obtained due to external geometry so it is called External Compression supersonic inlet.

If the compression takes place due to internal geometry it is known as Internal Compression supersonic inlet as shown in fig.2. In compression takes place both external and internal geometry of the intake it is known as Mixed Compression supersonic inlet as shown in the fig.3.

Fig.1: External Compression of supersonic inlet

Fig.2: Internal Compression of supersonic inlet

Fig.3: Mixed Compression of supersonic inlet

Mixed compression supersonic inlet increases pressure at outlet higher than the external compression and internal compression inlet. But these traditional supersonic inlet diffusers faces challenges related to achieving optimal pressure recovery value at suitable mach numbers at the inlet to the combustor. So, there is a need to have an optimal cowl and ramp design to obtain the highest performance of supersonic inlet diffuser , so further it can improve the ramjet engine performance. In this regard an attempt was made to obtain optimal cowl and ramp angles by 2D steady state numerical analysis on mixed compression supersonic inlet by Ansys fluent by varying cowl and ramp angles.

2. Methodology:

The input requirements, operating conditions, geometry selection, analysis and boundary conditions for mixed compression supersonic inlet are mentioned as shown in the fig.4. For present analysis a 2D axisymmetric Mixed compression supersonic inlet was numerically analysed through steady state, density based solver and k-omega(2eqn) SST viscous model.

Fig.4: Graphical representation of methodology

3. Numerical Setup:

Supersonic inlet diffuser was designed in ansys fluent and obtained 96453 nodes and 95302 elements as shown in the figure 4. Inlet was supplied with pressure of 8724 pa at mach number 4 for all the eight cases by varying cowl Angle(θ_1), fist Ramp Angle(θ_1) and second Ramp Angle (θ_2) as shown in the table1.

Fig.6: 2-D Sketch and geometry of Supersonic Inlet Diffuser

Table.1: Supersonic Inlet Diffuser Inlet Conditions

S.No	Inlet Free Pressure (P_1) (Pascals)	Free Stream Mach Number (M_∞)	Cowl Angle (θ_1) (Degrees)	Fist Ramp Angle (θ_1) (Degrees)	Second Ramp Angle (θ_2) (Degrees)
1	8724	4	11	3	21
2	8724	4	12	3	21
3	8724	4	13	3	21
4	8724	4	14	3	21
5	8724	4	13	4	21
6	8724	4	13	5	21
7	8724	4	13	4	22
8	8724	4	13	4	23

4. Results:

The outlet mach number and outlet pressure distributions are obtained at constant inlet static pressure of 8724 pa and free stream mach number of 4 for different cowl angle(11° , 12° , 13° , and 14°), first ramp angles(3° , 4° , and 5°) and second ramp angles(21° , 22° , and 23°). Numerical analysis was performed for different combination of cowl and ramp angles as shown in the table:1.

Fig.7: Mach number and pressure distribution in supersonic inlet diffuser for $\alpha_1=11^\circ$, $\alpha_1=3^\circ$, $\alpha_2=21^\circ$

Fig.8: Mach number and pressure distribution in supersonic inlet diffuser for $\alpha_1=12^\circ$, $\alpha_1=3^\circ$, $\alpha_2=21^\circ$

Fig.9: Mach number and pressure distribution in supersonic inlet diffuser for $\alpha_1=13^\circ$, $\alpha_1=3^\circ$, $\alpha_2=21^\circ$

Fig.10: Mach number and pressure distribution in supersonic inlet diffuser for $\alpha_1=14^\circ$, $\alpha_2=3^\circ$, $\alpha_3=21^\circ$

Fig.11: Mach number and pressure distribution in supersonic inlet diffuser for $\alpha_1=13^\circ$, $\alpha_2=4^\circ$, $\alpha_3=21^\circ$

Fig.12: Mach number and pressure distribution in supersonic inlet diffuser for $\alpha_1=13^\circ$, $\alpha_1=5^\circ$, $\alpha_2=21^\circ$

Fig.13: Mach number and pressure distribution in supersonic inlet diffuser for $\alpha_1=13^\circ$, $\alpha_1=4^\circ$, $\alpha_2=22^\circ$

Fig.14: Mach number and pressure distribution in supersonic inlet diffuser for $\alpha_1=13^\circ$, $\alpha_1=4^\circ$, $\alpha_2=23^\circ$

5. Discussion:

Outlet mach number, outlet stagnation pressure, pressure recovery were plotted against cowl angle, first and second ramp angles as shown in the figures 15, 16,17,18,19,20,21 ,22 and 23.

Fig.15:Outlet mach number variation at different first and second ramp angles of supersonic inlet.

Fig.16:Outlet stagnation pressure variation at different first and second ramp angles of supersonic inlet.

Fig.17:Pressure recovery variation at different first and second ramp angles of supersonic inlet.

Fig.18:Pressure recovery variation at different first ramp and cowl angles of supersonic inlet.

Fig.19:Outlet Stagnation pressure variation at different first ramp and cowl angles of supersonic inlet.

Fig.20:Outlet mach number variation at different first ramp and cowl angles of supersonic inlet.

Fig.21:Outlet mach number variation at different second ramp and cowl angles of supersonic inlet.

Fig.22:Outlet Stagnation pressure variation at different second ramp and cowl angles of supersonic inlet.

Fig.23: Pressure recovery variation at different second ramp and cowl angles of supersonic inlet.

At cowl angle 11° , first ramp angle 3° and second ramp angle 21° obtained highest pressure recovery 0.96 compared all other cases, but outlet mach number was 0.688. So this mach number is not suitable for combustion in ramjet engines. The suitable mach number nearer to combustion of ramjet engine are in the range of 0.3 to 0.4. At cowl angle 13° , first ramp angle 4° , second ramp angle 22° and 23° as shown in fig.13 and 14 given optimal mach numbers 0.315 and 0.417 respectively. Apart from second ramp angles 23° was taken optimal because pressure and mach number distribution were more uniform.

6. Conclusion:

Performance of supersonic inlet diffuser affects the performance of ramjet engines. Supersonic inlet diffuser performance is affected by geometry design of cowl and ramp. Supersonic inlet diffuser was analysed numerically at different cowl angle (11° , 12° , 13° , and 14°), first ramp angles (3° , 4° , and 5°) and second ramp angles (21° , 22° , and 23°) at

constant inlet static pressure of 8724 pa and free stream mach number of 4. Total pressure recovery , outlet mach number and outlet stagnation pressure were obtained for different cowl and ramp angle combinations. The optimal mach number 0.417 and pressure recovery 0.21 were obtained at cowl angle 13° , first ramp angle 4° , second ramp angle 23° because at these angles more uniform pressure and mach number were recorded.

List of abbreviations

Not applicable

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Declarations

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

References:

1. Jinsheng Zhang, Huacheng Yuan, Yunfei Wang, Guoping Huang, Experiment and numerical investigation of flow control on a supersonic inlet diffuser, Aerospace Science and Technology, Volume 106, 2020, 106182, ISSN 1270-9638, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2020.106182>.
2. Das, Sudip, and Jai Kumar Prasad. "Cowl Deflection Angle in a Supersonic Air Intake." Defence Science Journal 59.2 (2009).
3. Valorani, Mauro, et al. "Optimal supersonic intake design for air collection engines (ACE)." Acta Astronautica 45.12 (1999): 729-745..

4. Slater, John. "Design and analysis tool for external-compression supersonic inlets." *50th AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting including the New Horizons Forum and Aerospace Exposition*. 2012.
5. Ved Merchant and Jayakrishnan Radhakrishnan, Design and Optimization of Supersonic Intake, *2017 IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.* 225 012298
6. Alterations of cowl lip for the improvement of supersonic-intake performance, John B., Senthilkumar P.(2018) *Journal of Applied Fluid Mechanics*, 11 (1) , pp. 31-41.
7. JPS Sandhu, M Bhardwaj, N Ananthkrishnan, A Sharma, IS Park, Multi-Objective Aerodynamic Optimization of External Compression Supersonic Intake using Kriging/MOGA, *30 Jan 2024*
8. Bora O. Cakir, Ali Can Ispir, Bayindir H. Saracoglu, Reduced order design and investigation of intakes for high speed propulsion systems, *Acta Astronautica*, Volume 199, 2022, Pages 259-276, ISSN 0094-5765,
9. Chakraborty, D. (2020). CFD Methods in High-Speed Airbreathing Missile Propulsion Design. In: Gupta, A., De, A., Aggarwal, S., Kushari, A., Runchal, A. (eds) *Innovations in Sustainable Energy and Cleaner Environment*. Green Energy and Technology. Springer, Singapore
10. Mathew, Bilji C., et al. "Comparative performance analysis of supersonic inlets at various Mach number." *AIP Conference Proceedings*. Vol. 2962. No. 1. AIP Publishing, 2024.
11. Torp, Vegar Hagen. *Favourable design of the air intake of a ramjet*. MS thesis. NTNU, 2016.
12. INTAKES, PERFORMANCE OF SCRAMJET AIR. "Effect of Cowl angle in the performance of scramjet air intakes." *Technology* 8.11 (2017): 899-909.
13. Ma, Yue, et al. "Recent advances and prospects in hypersonic inlet design and intelligent optimization." *Aerospace Science and Technology* (2024): 108953.
14. Gahlot, Neeraj Kumar, and N. K. Singh. "Numerical study of supersonic mixed compression air intake with an array of air jets." *Journal of Fluids Engineering* 143.4 (2021): 041206.
15. Raju, Nandhini, Tonse Gokuldas Pai, and Verma SB. "An Experimental Investigation of Turbo-Ramjet Engine Intake at Mach 4." *AIAA Propulsion and Energy 2020 Forum*. 2020.
16. Shashi, V. Kumar, et al. "Aerodynamic design and optimization of supersonic inlets for external compression." *AIP Conference Proceedings*. Vol. 2204. No. 1. AIP Publishing, 2020.
17. Hasan, Zahraa Hamzah, et al. "Numerical Study of Air-Intake Performance of a Scramjet with Various Cowl Lip Length." *International Seminar on Aeronautics and Energy*. Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore, 2022.
18. Pattnaik, Subrat Partha Sarathi. *Design and Performance Investigation of Supersonic Air-Intakes*. Diss. 2022.

19. Zhi, Chen, et al. "Investigation on flows in a supersonic isolator with an adjustable cowl convergence angle." *Experimental thermal and fluid science* 52 (2014): 182-190.
20. CECCHETTO, PIETRO. "Hypersonic air intake design using multi-objective optimisation based on CFD data." (2021).